

Energy-efficient BLAS L1 Routines for FPGA-Supported HPC Applications*

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Abstract. Vector-based calculations dominate computations in scientific and industrial HPC software. However, up to now there are limited options for mapping them quickly and efficiently on FPGA-supported systems. This work presents a first set of FPGA kernels for mapping a large set of the BLAS L1 routine set on HPC FPGAs. All kernels retain exactly the same interface with respect to their software counterpart routine, whereas they can be configured in terms of internal computing engines. Results show that our kernels can achieve a speed up and performance-per-Watt ratio of up to 7x and 45x respectively, compared to Intel’s MKL routines when executed on server-class machines.

Keywords: BLAS routines · FPGA · HPC

1 Introduction and motivation

Vector based calculations dominate most computations in scientific and industrial software. However, up to now there are few options available on mapping such kernels on HPC FPGAs. Examples include the BLAS set from Xilinx that supports only 13 primitives [3], as well as the fBLAS [5] that supports BLAS routines for Intel FPGAs. This work will deliver 27 BLAS routines from levels L1, L2 and L3 that will be compatible with the latest HPC Xilinx FPGAs. The proposed library will retain the exact C-based API of the original BLAS routines to assist users on integration with existing development environments. As such, this paper presents a first set of results for 10 BLAS L1 routines that are implemented on U55c Alveo FPGA cards. Overall, the main contributions are below:

- A set of BLAS L1 hardware kernels that support HPC FPGAs (Section 2)
- Evaluation of the kernel set against server-class CPUs in terms of performance and performance-per-Watt (Section 3)

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2 Design Approach

This work is driven by the motivation of providing a set of hardware kernels that (i) can function as drop-in replacement for their software counterparts, and (ii) are configurable with respect to hardware resources and memory bandwidth utilization. For this reason, all hardware kernel calls are wrapped with software functions that expose the same input / output arguments with respect to the original BLAS routines. As shown in Algorithm 1 a wrapper is responsible for the following: (i) create N CUs, allocate input / output buffers, and transfer data from host to device memory (lines 1-5), (ii) start data processing, when data transfer is done (lines 7-9), and finally (iii) copy results back to the host memory (lines 11-13).

Algorithm 1 Software wrapper of BLAS L1 hardware kernels.

Require: BLAS routine input arguments, N

- 1: **for** i from 0 to N-1 **do**
- 2: create CU i
- 3: input / output buffer allocation in device memory for CU i
- 4: transfer input data to device memory
- 5: **end for**
- 6: sync_barrier
- 7: **for** i from 0 to N-1 **do**
- 8: start CU i
- 9: **end for**
- 10: sync_barrier
- 11: **for** i from 0 to N-1 **do**
- 12: transfer output data to host memory
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **return** success ? 0 : -1

Furthermore, as an example, Figure 1 illustrates the axpy and scal kernels design approach with respect to CUs utilization, and HBM channel allocation and access. Every axpy CU kernel requires 2 input and 1 output HBM channels. However, since the kernel overwrites input data with the newly calculated results, the 2nd input and output share the same HBM channel. Consequently, for N CUs the axpy kernel will use $2N-1$ HBM channels. Similarly, each CU of the scal kernel requires only a single HBM channel, since input data are multiplied by a scalar and the results overwrites previously stored data. As such, for M CUs the scal kernel will utilize M HBM channels.

This flexibility allows developers to instantiate a set kernels with different CUs that can be customized based on the expected workload. For example, consider an application that uses the axpy and iamax kernels, and the axpy workload is 4x compared to the one of iamax; in this case, the kernels can be configured with 4 and 1 CUs respectively, in order to match as close as possible processing demands.

Fig. 1. Examples of the axpy and scal BLAS L1 kernels interfacing the FPGA’s HBM.

3 Experimental Results

All BLAS L1 routines were developed with high-level synthesis (HLS) and the Xilinx Vitis 2022.1 environment, and implemented on a U55C Xilinx FPGA board with 16 GB of HBM available. As discussed, all kernels instantiate a configurable number of low-resource CUs that may be limited only by the total number of available HBM channels.

Towards evaluating our kernels, we compared all BLAS L1 kernels against Intel’s Math Kernel Library (MKL) [4] BLAS L1 routines optimized for multi-threaded execution on an Intel Xeon Gold 5120 at 2.2 GHz host CPU, with respect to execution time and performance-per-Watt. All experiments use vector sizes of 67M single-precision floating point elements. Power consumption on the host CPU was measured with the turbostat utility [1], whereas on the U55C with Xilinx’s xbutil commands [2]. The performance-per-Watt (PpW) ratio between the U55C and host CPU is calculated using the following equation:

$$\frac{PpW_{FPGA}}{PpW_{CPU}} = \frac{\frac{P_{FPGA}}{W_{FPGA}}}{\frac{P_{CPU}}{W_{CPU}}} = \frac{P_{FPGA}}{P_{CPU}} \cdot \frac{W_{CPU}}{W_{FPGA}} = S \cdot \frac{W_{CPU}}{W_{FPGA}} \quad (1)$$

where in equation (1), P_{FPGA} and P_{CPU} are the FPGA and CPU performance respectively, S is the FPGA speedup vs the host CPU, and W_{FPGA} and W_{CPU} are the FPGA and CPU power consumption respectively.

Figure 2 shows the speedup, ppW and number of CUs instantiated for all BLAS L1 kernels. As shown, complex kernels like the sddot and dot require 3 HBM channels / CU, allowing up to 10 CUs to fit within a single U55C. All other kernels (except scal) require 2 HBM channels / CU, thus increasing the total number of CUs to 16.

With respect to kernel performance, the copy, swap, and rot kernels show a speedup of 7x, whereas scal, axpy and rotm improve performance 6x, 4x and 2.5x respectively. Moreover, the dot and sddot kernels show marginal speedup of 50% and 30% respectively. Finally, the asum, iamax and nrm2 kernels are approximately 2 times slower compared to the software version.

However, it should be noted that for all kernels, the PpW_{FPGA} is always improved compared to the PpW_{CPU} . As shown, in Figure 2, kernels that are even slower compared to the CPU (nrm2, iamax, asum) achieve more than 2x better performance-per-Watt compared to the CPU. Whereas kernels that scale

Fig. 2. Experimental results for all BLAS L1 routines when compared against the host CPU implementation.

efficiently (e.g. copy and swap) boost ppW up to 45x, making this library implementation an optimal choice for deploying performance and energy-efficient FPGA-based HPC systems. It should be noted that the current implementations support only single-precision floating point arithmetic.

4 Conclusions and future work

As shown, our BLAS L1 FPGA routines allow developers to use quickly and efficiently the power of HPC FPGA platforms. With respect to programmability, the library set exposes an API that is identical to the original BLAS routines. Finally, they can achieve a speedup and performance-per-Watt up to 7x and 35x respectively compared to server-class CPUs. Our future work focuses on optimizing a large set of the BLAS L2 and L3 routines on HPC FPGAs that will be fully compatible with their software counterparts with respect to their input / output parameters.

References

1. turbostat - report processor frequency and idle statistics (2023), <https://www.linux.org/docs/man8/turbostat.html>
2. xbutil commands (2023), <https://xilinx.github.io/XRT/master/html/xbutil.html>
3. Xilinx blas library (2023), https://xilinx.github.io/Vitis_Libraries/blas/2022.1/user_guide/L1/L1_compute_api.html
4. Intel Crp.: Intel math kernel library (mkl) (2023), <https://software.intel.com/en-us/intel-mkl>
5. Tiziano De Matteis, Johannes de Fine Licht, Torsten Hoefer: Fblas: Streaming linear algebra on fpga. In: International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis (2020)